

Enterprise Applications of Deep-Learning

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

From its inception, Deep Learning has yielded the potential to massively disrupt the way Enterprises function. This has been the single greatest advancement since the dawn of personal computing, and for the first time in history, will affect the meaning of a “White-Collar Jobs.” Deep Learning defines the automation of many aspects of work in fields such as Healthcare & Institutional Finance. From reading your X-Rays to investing your money, Deep-learning will drive this change.

2. Aim

Review the current state of the Enterprise and how technological advancement with deep learning will evolve the Enterprise. This talk will dive into specific examples and use-cases of deep learning while demonstrating the expected outcome.

3. Material and methods

AI Labs Inc evaluated four different industries and conceived solutions for problems facing those industries, these are including but not limited to, Law (legaltech), Wealth Management & Institutional Finance (Fintech), Medicine & Healthcare (Healthtech) and Insurance (Insuretech). We analyzed the industries current workflow, technological capabilities & automation standards and ran case studies on how Deep-learning would affect their workforce, productivity, capital efficiency and the overall business. Case studies contained mock-simulations with DeepLearning applications involved, both with real software and mock-software based on real-world applications. Examples of deep-learning applications were automated portfolio construction & management, Legal Case Analysis, and automated claim-management & compliance. Based on the implementation of these technologies into the hands of case-groups we were able to determine how they would be adopted and how they would evolve the groups themselves.

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4. Results

Results were very interesting, many of the existing workflows produced by associates and other lower-tier members of the workforce were shown to be automated. A reduction in headcount and transfer of great “human” interfacing towards the top of the pyramid started to take place. Costcutting and labor reduction allowed the group more flexibility and higher-margins. Higher quality work and product was also delivered; wealth management, in particular, demonstrated that advisors could offer clients higher-quality investment solutions at a fraction of the cost and time previous to their implementation. Results were unsettling, yet refreshing in that although there would be workforce reduction, the organization would be better off for it.

5. Conclusions

Albeit, these weren't real and just case studies, the results showed that deep-learning with drive serious change in major organizations. The top of the pyramid will benefit the most while more mundane tasks done by the lowers tiers will cease to exists. Higher Quality standards and products will be delivered at a fraction of the time and cost, benefiting both the client and company.

6. Keywords

Deep Learning; Fintech; Legaltech; Artificial Intelligence; Enterprise

Author biography

Samir Vasavada Samir Vasavada is Co-Founder & CEO of Ai labs, Inc. In his respective position, Samir is responsible for devising new development strategies, managing operations, establishing the culture, and managing company relations. More so, Samir helps develop financial strategies to optimize Portfolio Construction. Prior to Ai Labs, Inc, Samir founded Centrix/NYX Group, a global technologies firm specializing in Marketing and Software solutions. NYX consults with businesses for software development and marketing strategies. He oversaw a large international team of developers and projects.

After NYX, Samir and a partner created Copydoc, an AI character recognition solution utilizing guess-based analysis to recognize characters and accurately construct sentences. The focus of his project was to prevent the need for extensive copying of handwritten documents to a text-based environment.

Samir sits on advisory boards of several SaaS and Web startups. He is also a buy side consultant with GLG and Coleman Research. He consults with financial organizations such as banks,

brokerage firms and hedge funds on topics such as digital marketing, AI market trends/AI's integration into enterprise, and new types of data analysis for better understanding and valuing a security.

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Prior to Samir's ventures, he took courses at Northwestern in Computer Science, and Documentary Filmmaking. Samir subsequently won awards in Robotics, Software Development, and in Business competitions.

Samir loves crypto trading, making new iOS apps, filmmaking and golf.

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